

DYNAMIC PROPAGATION OF A WEAK-DISCONTINUOUS INTERFACE CRACK IN FUNCTIONALLY GRADED LAYERS UNDER ANTI-PLANE SHEAR

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1 Introduction

Functionally graded materials (FGMs) have been recently attracted extensive attention for use in high temperature applications and wear-protective coatings. The FGMs are microscopically non-homogeneous because the mechanical properties of the FGM vary smoothly and continuously. The fracture behavior of the FGM is important design issue. A crack in the FGM may exhibit complex behavior because of the variation of the mechanical properties of the material. The fracture behaviors of the FGMs have been studied widely for both static and dynamic problems. But, solution of the dynamic crack propagation of an interface crack between two dissimilar functionally graded layers has not been presented.

In this paper, dynamic propagation of an interface Griffith crack between two functionally graded layers under anti-plane shear is analyzed. The properties of the functionally graded layers vary continuously along the thickness. In addition, the properties of the two functionally graded layers vary differently and the two layers are connected weak-discontinuously (Li et al.[1]). The Yoffe-type model (Yoffe[2]) for crack propagation is adopted. Fourier transform is used to reduce the problem to a dual integral equation, which is then expressed in a Fredholm integral equation of the second kind. Numerical results of the dynamic energy release rate are presented graphically to show the effect of gradient of material properties, crack moving velocity, and thickness of layers.

2 Problem statement and formulations

Consider two functionally graded layers containing a finite interface crack subjected to anti-plane shear loading, as shown in Fig. 1. Material properties of the two functionally graded layers vary differently. The Cartesian coordinates (X, Y, Z) are fixed for the reference. The FGM layers occupy the region, $-\infty < X < \infty$, $-h_2 \leq Y \leq h_1$, and are thick enough in the Z -direction. The crack is situated along the interface line $(-a \leq X \leq a, Y=0)$. Due to the symmetry in geometry and loading, it is sufficient to consider the right-hand half body only.

Fig. 1. Geometry of a constant moving interface crack between two functionally graded layers

We assume that the properties of the two functionally graded layers vary continuously along the thickness and are simplified as follows (Delale and Erdogan[3]):

$$\mu_i = \mu_0 e^{\beta_i Y} \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_i = \rho_0 e^{\beta_i Y} \quad (2)$$

where μ_i and ρ_i are the shear modulus and material density, respectively. μ_0 and ρ_0 are the material

properties at the interface and β_i is the non-homogeneous material constant. Subscript $i(i=1,2)$ stands for the upper and lower layers, respectively. The boundary value problem is simplified considerably if we consider only the out-of-plane displacement such that

$$u_{xi} = u_{yi} = 0, \quad u_{zi} = w_i(X, Y, t) \quad (3)$$

where u_{ki} ($k = X, Y, Z$) is the displacements. In this case, the constitutive relation becomes

$$\sigma_{zji}(X, Y, t) = \mu_i w_{i,j} \quad (4)$$

where σ_{zji} ($j = X, Y$) is the stress component.

The dynamic anti-plane governing equation for FGM is simplified to

$$\mu_i \nabla^2 w_i + \beta_i \mu_i \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial Y} = \rho_i \frac{\partial^2 w_i}{\partial t^2} \quad (5)$$

where $\nabla^2 = \partial^2 / \partial X^2 + \partial^2 / \partial Y^2$.

By substituting Eqs. (1) and (2) into the Eq. (5), the dynamic governing equation is transformed into the following equation:

$$\nabla^2 w_i + \beta_i \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial Y} = \frac{1}{c_2^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_i}{\partial t^2} \quad (6)$$

where

$$c_2 = \sqrt{\mu_0 / \rho_0} \quad (7)$$

and c_2 is the shear wave velocity.

For the problem of a moving crack with constant velocity “ v ” along the X -direction, it is convenient to introduce a Galilean transformation such as

$$x = X - vt, \quad y = Y, \quad z = Z, \quad t = t \quad (8)$$

where (x, y, z) is the translating coordinate system attached to the center of the moving crack.

In the transformed coordinate system, the dynamic anti-plane governing equation for FGM can be simplified to the following form:

$$\alpha^2 \frac{\partial^2 w_i(x, y)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w_i(x, y)}{\partial y^2} + \beta_i \frac{\partial w_i(x, y)}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where

$$\alpha = \sqrt{1 - (v/c_2)^2} \quad (10)$$

A Fourier transform is applied to Eq. (9), and the result is as follows:

$$w_i(x, y) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty [A_{1i}(s)e^{-q_{1i}y} + A_{2i}(s)e^{q_{2i}y}] \cos(sx) ds \quad (11)$$

where

$$q_{1i} = \delta_i + \frac{\beta_i}{2}, \quad q_{2i} = \delta_i - \frac{\beta_i}{2} \quad (12)$$

$$\delta_i = \sqrt{\alpha^2 s^2 + \frac{\beta_i^2}{4}} \quad (13)$$

A_{1i} and A_{2i} are the unknowns to be solved.

By substituting Eq. (11) for Eq. (4), we have the following:

$$\sigma_{yzi}(x, y) = \mu_0 \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty [-q_{1i} A_{1i}(s)e^{-q_{2i}y} + q_{2i} A_{2i}(s)e^{q_{1i}y}] \cos(sx) ds \quad (14)$$

The boundary conditions can be written as

$$\sigma_{yzi}(x, 0) = -\tau_0 \quad (0 \leq x < a) \quad (15)$$

$$w_1(x, 0^+) = w_2(x, 0^-) \quad (a < x \leq \infty) \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_{yz1}(x, 0^+) = \sigma_{yz2}(x, 0^-) \quad (a < x \leq \infty) \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_{yz1}(x, h_1) = \sigma_{yz2}(x, -h_2) = 0 \quad (0 < x \leq \infty) \quad (18)$$

where τ_0 is the uniform shear traction.

By applying the edge loading conditions of Eq. (18), the unknowns in Eq. (14) are evaluated as follows:

$$-q_{11} A_{11}(s)e^{-q_{21}h_1} + q_{21} A_{21}(s)e^{q_{11}h_1} = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$-q_{12} A_{12}(s)e^{q_{22}h_2} + q_{22} A_{22}(s)e^{-q_{12}h_2} = 0 \quad (20)$$

The continuity condition of Eq. (17) leads to the following relation between the unknowns:

$$-q_{11} A_{11}(s) + q_{21} A_{21}(s) = -q_{12} A_{12}(s) + q_{22} A_{22}(s) \quad (21)$$

It is convenient to use the following definitions:

$$\Omega(\xi) + \int_0^a K(\xi, \eta) \Omega(\eta) d\eta = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{2}{\alpha} \frac{\tau_0}{\mu_0} \quad (30)$$

$$A_{11}(s) - A_{12}(s) + A_{21}(s) - A_{22}(s) = A(s) \quad (22)$$

where

$$K(\xi, \eta) = \eta \int_0^\infty s [F(s) - 1] J_0(s\eta) J_0(s\xi) ds \quad (31)$$

Using the Eqs. (19) to (22), we can obtain the following relations:

$$A_{11}(s) = \frac{q_{12}q_{21}q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\delta_2 h_2})}{q_{11}q_{21}(1 - e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})(q_{12} + q_{22}e^{-2\delta_2 h_2}) + q_{12}q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\delta_2 h_2})(q_{21} + q_{11}e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})} A(s) \quad (23)$$

$$A_{12}(s) = \frac{-q_{11}q_{21}q_{22}e^{-2\delta_2 h_2}(1 - e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})}{q_{11}q_{21}(1 - e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})(q_{12} + q_{22}e^{-2\delta_2 h_2}) + q_{12}q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\delta_2 h_2})(q_{21} + q_{11}e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})} A(s) \quad (24)$$

$$A_{21}(s) = \frac{q_{11}q_{12}q_{22}e^{-2\delta_1 h_1}(1 - e^{-2\delta_2 h_2})}{q_{11}q_{21}(1 - e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})(q_{12} + q_{22}e^{-2\delta_2 h_2}) + q_{12}q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\delta_2 h_2})(q_{21} + q_{11}e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})} A(s) \quad (25)$$

$$A_{22}(s) = \frac{-q_{11}q_{12}q_{21}(1 - e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})}{q_{11}q_{21}(1 - e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})(q_{12} + q_{22}e^{-2\delta_2 h_2}) + q_{12}q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\delta_2 h_2})(q_{21} + q_{11}e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})} A(s) \quad (26)$$

The mixed boundary conditions of Eqs. (15) and (16) lead to a dual integral equations in the following form:

$$\int_0^\infty s F(s) A(s) \cos(sx) ds = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{2}{\alpha} \frac{\tau_0}{\mu_0} \quad (0 \leq x < a)$$

$$\int_0^\infty A(s) \cos(sx) ds = 0 \quad (a < x \leq \infty) \quad (27)$$

where

$$F(s) = \frac{2}{\alpha} \frac{1}{s} \left[\frac{q_{11}q_{12}q_{21}q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})(1 - e^{-2\delta_2 h_2})}{q_{11}q_{21}(1 - e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})(q_{12} + q_{22}e^{-2\delta_2 h_2}) + q_{12}q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\delta_2 h_2})(q_{21} + q_{11}e^{-2\delta_1 h_1})} \right] \quad (28)$$

The dual integral Eq. (27) may be solved by using new function $\Omega(\xi)$ defined by

$$A(s) = \int \xi \Omega(\xi) J_0(s\xi) d\xi \quad (29)$$

where J_0 is the zero-order Bessel function of the first kind.

By inserting Eq. (29) into Eq. (27), we can find that the auxiliary function $\Omega(\xi)$ is given by a Fredholm integral equation of the second kind in the following form:

We introduce the following dimensionless variables and function for numerical analysis as follows:

$$s = \frac{S}{a}, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{B_1}{a}, \quad \beta_2 = \frac{B_2}{a}, \quad \delta_1 = \frac{\Delta_1}{a}, \quad \delta_2 = \frac{\Delta_2}{a} \quad (32)$$

$$\eta = aH, \quad \xi = a\xi \quad (33)$$

$$\Omega(\xi) = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{2}{\alpha} \frac{\tau_0}{\mu_0} \frac{\Psi(\Xi)}{\sqrt{\Xi}} \quad (34)$$

By substituting Eqs. (32) to (34) for Eqs. (30) and (31), we can obtain a Fredholm integral equation of the second kind in the following form:

$$\Psi(\Xi) + \int_0^1 L(\Xi, H) \Psi(H) dH = \sqrt{\Xi} \quad (35)$$

where

$$L(\Xi, H) = \sqrt{\Xi H} \int_0^\infty S \left[F\left(\frac{S}{a}\right) - 1 \right] J_0(SH) J_0(S\Xi) dS \quad (36)$$

$$F\left(\frac{S}{a}\right) = \frac{2}{\alpha} \frac{1}{S} \left[\frac{Q_{11}Q_{12}Q_{21}Q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\Delta_1 \frac{h_1}{a}})(1 - e^{-2\Delta_2 \frac{h_2}{a}})}{Q_{11}Q_{21}(1 - e^{-2\Delta_1 \frac{h_1}{a}})(Q_{12} + Q_{22}e^{-2\Delta_2 \frac{h_2}{a}}) + Q_{12}Q_{22}(1 - e^{-2\Delta_2 \frac{h_2}{a}})(Q_{21} + Q_{11}e^{-2\Delta_1 \frac{h_1}{a}})} \right] \quad (37)$$

$$Q_{11} = \Delta_1 + \frac{B_1}{2}, \quad Q_{12} = \Delta_2 + \frac{B_2}{2}, \quad Q_{21} = \Delta_1 - \frac{B_1}{2}, \quad Q_{22} = \Delta_2 - \frac{B_2}{2} \quad (38)$$

The mode III dynamic stress intensity factor $K_{III}(v)$ and dynamic energy release rate $G_{III}(v)$ are defined and determined in the following forms:

$$K_{III}(v) = \tau_0 \sqrt{\pi a} \Psi(1) \quad (39)$$

$$G_{III}(v) = \frac{\pi a}{2\mu_0} \tau_0^2 \Psi^2(1) \quad (40)$$

Eq. (40) can be made dimensionless as follow:

$$\frac{G_{III}(v) 2\mu_0}{\tau_0^2 \pi a} = \Psi^2(1) \quad (41)$$

in which the function $\Psi(1)$ can be calculated from Eq. (35).

3 Discussions

To investigate the effect of the gradient of material properties, crack moving velocity and thickness of layers on the dynamic energy release rate (DERR), numerical analyses are carried out.

Fig. 2 displays the variation of the normalized DERR $G_{III}(v) 2\mu_0 / \tau_0^2 \pi a$ against the normalized non-homogeneous material constant of the upper layer B_1 with various normalized non-homogeneous material constants of the lower layer B_2 at $v/c_2 = 0.4$ and $h_1/a = h_2/a = 10.0$. The normalized DERR decreases when the gradients of material properties of the upper and lower layers increase. For the upper layer, the gradient of material properties increases as the non-homogeneous material constant increases. But for the lower layer, the gradient of material properties increases as the non-homogeneous material constant decreases because value of the y-axis is negative. Increase of the gradient of material properties from the interface

is beneficial to increase of the resistance of the interface crack propagation of FGM.

Fig. 2. Variation of the normalized DERR $G_{III}(v) 2\mu_0 / \tau_0^2 \pi a$ with B_1

Fig. 3 shows the variation of the normalized DERR against the normalized crack moving velocity v/c_2 with the various normalized non-homogeneous material constants. According to the values of the gradient of material properties of the upper and lower layer, we can classify into three categories as follows:

- Case I : material properties increase when the thickness of upper and lower layer increases from the interface,
- Case II : material properties decrease when the thickness of upper and lower layer increases from the interface,
- Case III : material properties increase from the lower surface ($y = -h_2$) to upper surface

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($y = h_1$), and vice versa.

For the Case II and III, the normalized DERR increases as the crack moving velocity increases. But for the Case I, the trend is opposite. The normalized DERR decreases when the crack moving velocity increases. That is, increase of the stiffness from the interface to the upper and lower surface is helpful to increase of the resistance of the interface crack propagation of FGM. As the absolute value of B_2/B_1 increases, that is, the difference between the gradients of the material properties of upper and lower layer is getting bigger, the normalized DERR increases or decreases more rapidly.

Fig. 3. Variation of the normalized DERR $G_{III}(v) 2\mu_0/\tau_0^2 \pi a$ with v/c_2

The effect of the crack moving velocity on the variation of the normalized DERR is shown in Fig. 4 with various thicknesses of the layers. The normalized DERR increases with the increase of the crack moving velocity. But the normalized DERR decreases when the thickness of layer increases. Increase of the thickness of FGM layer is also beneficial to increase of the resistance of the interface crack propagation of FGM.

Fig. 5 presents the variation of the normalized DERR against the normalized thickness of the lower FGM layer with the various non-homogeneous material constants. Similar to Fig. 4, the normalized DERR decreases as the thickness of the lower layer increases. But, over certain value of the thickness of

the lower layer (about 3.00), the effect of decrease of the normalized DERR is negligible. As seen in Case I of Fig. 3, Fig. 5 also shows that increase of the stiffness from the interface to the upper and lower surface is helpful to increase of the resistance of the interface crack propagation of FGM.

Fig. 4. Variation of the normalized DERR $G_{III}(v) 2\mu_0/\tau_0^2 \pi a$ with v/c_2

Fig. 5. Variation of the normalized DERR $G_{III}(v) 2\mu_0/\tau_0^2 \pi a$ with h_2/a

4 Conclusions

The problem of dynamic propagation of a weak-

discontinuous interface crack between two functionally graded layers under anti-plane shear loading was analyzed by the integral transform approach. The shear modulus and mass density of the FGM vary continuously along the thickness. A Fredholm integral equation is solved numerically. The computed results show that the followings are helpful to increase of the resistance of the interface crack propagation of FGM:

- a) Increase of the gradient of material properties,
- b) Increase of the material properties from the interface to the upper and lower free surface,
- c) Increase of the thickness of FGM layer.

The normalized DERR increases or decreases with increase of crack moving velocity.

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